

An Overview of Ethics and Principals in Yoga Philosophy

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ABSTRACT

Although there is no separate discussion of ethics in Indian philosophy, there is a discussion of ethics and various behavioral restrictions centered on attaining salvation. Since in Indian philosophy the ultimate goal is moksha, there is much discussion in the branch of philosophy about the bondage and liberation of the soul. Self-realization is by no means possible without the practice of the rules, so within the eight limbs of yoga philosophy, the practice of yama and niyama vidhi contains sufficient indications of ethics. And an attempt has been made to make that point clear in this article. Physical discipline in asana, pranayama, and pratyahar. By all these practices only physical purity helps to attain mental purity. And the observance of these moral restrictions ultimately leads to self-knowledge. Thus the jivatma is freed from the bondage, and all cittavrittis are restrained.

KEYWORDS: Moral-behavior, Bond and Release, Ashtangikayoga, Self-realization, Mindfulness, Yama

INTRODUCTION

Ethics word is comes from the Greek word ethika. The root word of ethics is ethos which means character. Again the synonym of this word Ethics is Moral Philosophy. The word mores means customs and duties etc. However, ethics is about those things about which people use adjectives like good and bad, should and should not. However, humans are social creatures who prefer to live in groups. All people living in the same society follow similar customs. Ethics becomes necessary to evaluate the behavior and norms of society. Whenever this evaluation is done against the criteria of right and wrong, it becomes a matter of ethics.

Thus yoga philosophy, one of the branches of Indian philosophy, also discusses ethics inherent in yama and niyama. In yoga philosophy, when Ashtangika yoga is mentioned in the context of the path of freedom from the bonds of the soul, we find hints of ethics in the rules of yama and niyama. Therefore, through the discussion of yoga philosophy, there is a wide discussion of the evaluation of actions and the aspects of right and wrong.

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Objective

1. Clarifying the discussion of prohibitions of action in the branch of yoga philosophy as in every branch of Indian philosophy.
2. There is no other way to attain salvation and self-realization than the practice of moral principles.
3. To point out that ethics are closely related to discussions in other branches of philosophy.

Cause of Bondage

According to Sankhya-yoga, the living being is possessed of a free (mukta) and unattached soul, the soul is free from both gross and subtle bodies. The intellect, mind and ego comprise the subtle body. For non-knowledge or avidya the soul is considered to be united with the intellect. Buddhi (Chitta) is the first result of Prakriti and sattva guna predominates among sattva, rajah and tama guna. The mind is unconscious in nature but being so close to the soul the consciousness of the soul is reflected in the mind, and then it appears to be conscious. Chitta and mind are different, when Chitta is connected with an object through mind, it takes the form of that object, through this form of Chitta or vrtti we get knowledge of the object. When the moon is reflected in the moving wave, the moon appears to be in motion, and even

though the soul is not perturbed or changed, it appears to be as changeable as the mind to reflect the mind in the conscious soul. In this way we get attracted to all the worldly things and get caught in the net of illusion of the world to get them. The soul fails to know its own nature. This condition is called bonding. The only way to get rid of this bond is to practice yoga.

Eightfold Yoga

To liberate the soul from these bonds or to realize the soul's own nature, Yoga philosophy mentions eight yoga limbs by which Chittavrtti can be restrained. And more is thought that In yoga philosophy, the soul is completely different from the body, mind, senses-organ and intellect. Self-realization is achieved only when Samyaktjñana is attained. That is, when all ignorance is removed, the soul gains knowledge of its own nature. For this reason yoga philosophy prescribes ashtavida yoganga emulation. The first five of these eight vidhis are known external practices, And the remaining three are intimate realizations. These are discussed in sequence below, viz Yama, Niyam, Asana, Pranayam, Pratyahara, Dhyana, Dhyana and Samadhi are the Ashtavida Yoga of Yoga philosophy.

Yama (RESTRAINT):

Yama generally refers to prohibited acts, Yama is done in the name of abstaining from certain actions in particular. Again, as part of this Yama, there are five prohibitions mentioned. The first is non-violence(Ahimsa), That is, to stay away from all forms of Jiva or living being violence. The second Yamas is truth(Satya), That is, do not lie. Third Yamas is Astaya, do not waste or steal. Fourth is Bramacharya, practicing celibacy and being free from sensual desires That is, to withdraw from the specific objects that each sense-organs has And the fifth is Aparigraha, i. e. not taking anything extra from others unnecessarily. These are the parts of Yama practice. It is said in Bhagavad Gita that if anyone cannot be freed from anger, hatred etc. then that man cannot become stable wise, so the necessity of practicing Yama to gain wisdom cannot be denied in any way.

Niyama (Culture):

Niyama means practicing some higher quality or realizing the significance of some precepts.

These are as follows-

First of all, Saucha i. e. those things or matters that can be physically and mentally purified if practiced. such as physical purification by bathing, sāttbika āhāra, external purification etc. And good luck to others, show kindness, Achieving peace of mind by giving up anger, greed etc. Second is Santosha, contentment or being satisfied with little. Thirdly is Tapas, the observance of austerities. Fourth is

Svadyaya, its mean self-study or other austerities, Such as daily reading of scriptures. Fifth, Ishvara Pranidhana or remembrance of God, contemplation and surrender to God are part of the practice of discipline (Niyama). For the practice of yoga, not only abstinence from certain actions, but also doing some auspicious actions is part of yoga, hence observance of (Niyama) rules is mentioned.

Āsana (Posture):

As such, it is not possible to concentrate on any one thing for a long time, Therefore, in order to concentrate on a subject for a long time, it is necessary to adopt a special sitting posture, so asana practice is prescribed in yoga philosophy.

Prāṇāyāma (Breath Control):

Pranayama is a special process of controlling the breath. The pranayama process is divided into three parts, namely Pūraka, kumbhaka and rēcaka. The process of Inhalation is called Puraka. The process of holding the breath for a long time is called kumbhaka, And the process of exhalation is called laxative. Repeated practice of this process improves and increases heart rate. If the Kumbhaka process is properly mastered, introspective thinking is enhanced. And for long periods of introspection, the process of pranayama is of considerable importance in yoga philosophy. So Pranayama is prescribed in yoga philosophy.

Pratyāhāra (Withdrawal of Senses):

Pratyāhāra refers to turning the senses away from their sense-perceptible objects. We know that each sense has different sense objects. And withdrawing the senses from all those sense-perceived things. such as, visual is Form with eyes, The ear deals with sound, the nose deals with smell, the gut deals with taste and the skin deals with touch. When the various senses-organ are directed towards these various things, the mind becomes deranged and in this state it is not possible to think inwardly, that is why yoga philosophy mentions the rule of withdrawal to control the senses.

Dhāraṇā (Attention):

Dhāraṇā means concentration on one thing. Just as one's own body parts can be the subject of ideas, external things like the idols of gods and goddesses can also be the subject of ideas. The ability to concentrate on a single subject for a long period of time entitles the ascetic to enter into higher thoughts. A person who cannot concentrate on any one thing or object for long is unfit for higher thought or yoga practice, That is why the need for ideas or Dhāraṇā in yoga philosophy is undeniable.

Dhyāna(Contemplation):

Initiation of continuous thought on a subject is called meditation. This leads first to a thorough knowledge of the parts of the subject of thought and then to the knowledge of the whole subject. As a result of long meditation the subject becomes clear and the thinking subject then seems alive. The sadhaka then saw an awakened image of the treasure of sadhana. Ultimately, there is no other way to realize one's own nature than transcendental meditation.

Samādhi(Concentration):

The last stage of Sadhana is called Samādhi.

In this state the mind becomes so absorbed in the meditation that it loses its individuality and considers the object of meditation and the Sadhak or saint to be one and the same. Then let the object of meditation and the saint become one. In this state the soul can realize itself. And then the master of meditation in the soul and so the object of meditation. That is, all beings become soulful. Finally, this mindset or Cittabṛttira is curbed.

Queries of ethics in Yoga philosophy

Realization of self-knowledge is not possible without moral restrictions. Hence the first two of the Ashtavid yogas contain glimpses of morality, Namely, yamas prescribe restrictions on conduct and niyamas refer to actions to be performed. On the other hand physical control is prescribed by asana, pranayama and Pratyāhāra or retraction. The purpose of observing Yama Vidhi is to abstain from immoral actions. Those are, first, non-violence i. e. all beings are free from violence because to be involved in violent activities is to be involved in immoral activities. Love and beneficence towards living beings is moral action. Second is truth i. e. not telling lies, always telling the truth is moral action. Lies can never instill good qualities in anyone. Therefore, we should not slander others, speak falsely about others. Even thinking ill of others is an immoral act, so one should be careful to speak the truth while keeping a distance from lying. Third, do not steal. Stealing i. e. taking another's property without permission should not be done because taking another's property without permission is considered an immoral act. Taking a bad look at other people's property is an immoral act, so all such acts should be avoided. The fourth is celibacy, i. e. take restrictions from sensual desires. Each sense has specific sense-perceptible objects towards which the mind moves like a madman. So keeping the senses- organ away from all those things, Because without practicing celibacy, good qualities cannot emerge in people. The moral action of imparting good qualities which is possible through the practice of celibacy. The important behavior to

follow after celibacy is aparigraha i. e. not taking anything extra from others unnecessarily. All these are forbidden works. The rule of morality is to refrain from doing evil and to do good. Yoga philosophy advises the practice of niyamas to perform those actions which are beneficial so that auspicious qualities can arise in us. These are: First, ablution i. e. those things which are practiced to maintain physical and mental purity. Second, contentment or being satisfied with little. There is no end to wanting more so we must be content with less. Thirdly, performing austerities. Fourthly, doing svadhyaya or daily scripture reading etc, And fifthly, Ishwar Pranidhana is part of the practice of remembrance of God, contemplation and surrender to God. For the practice of yoga not only abstinence from certain actions but also doing some auspicious actions is a part of yoga hence observance of rules(Niyama) is mentioned. Asana, pranayam and withdrawal(Pratyahara) are the methods of physical discipline. The sitting technique can be mastered in different ways by asana. Learn to master the technique of breath control through pranayama. Again by practicing withdrawal (Pratyahara) we learn to control the senses organ. So it can be said that the good-bad, right-wrong and proper-improper aspects of our behavior are mentioned in Yama and Niyama, just like the undisputed subject of ethics. Since Indian philosophy is basically spiritual, attaining moksha as the ultimate goal is considered the only desirable thing, so even if ethics is not developed separately, in yoga philosophy focusing on the process of attaining moksha, evidence of justice is found in the observance of Ashtanga Vidhi. Just as western philosophy has a separate discussion of ethics, Indian philosophy does not, but in Indian philosophy too, self-realization is not possible without the discussion of ethics.

Conclusion

There are differences between Indian and Western philosophies on the discussion of ethics. Western philosophy has a separate branch of ethics, where practical and theoretical ethics are discussed. For ethical analysis and judgment of various actions there are should-shouldn't adjectives. Thus there is no separate discussion of ethics in Indian philosophy. In Indian philosophy there is a discussion of ethics centered around the issue of moksha or liberation. Moreover, it is also true that due to the fact that right action is superior to wrong action, the righteous person has been advised the right path. However, in any case, the yama vidhi of yoga philosophy mentions what actions should not be done and the niyama vidhi mentions what actions should be done or observed. Just as Jain philosophy prohibits actions through the observance of Anuvrata and Mahavrata,

Buddhist philosophy refers to the Eightfold Path, whose moral form is the Panchasila, with its focus on attaining Nirvana, which prohibits similar actions. Finally, it can be said with certainty that no branch of Indian philosophy is devoid of principle of ethics, but to attain supreme purpose (Purusartha) and self-knowledge, it is in no way possible without performing moral actions.

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